

Low-cost, High Strength Polyacrylonitrile Precursor Fibre

H. Khan^{1,2}, J. Kaur², R. Varley¹, S. Hutchinson², M. Naebe¹

¹Institute of Frontier Materials, Deakin University, Waurn Ponds, Australia

²CSIRO, Waurn Ponds, Australia

Introduction

- Carbon fibres are unique reinforcing agents for lightweight composite materials due to their outstanding mechanical properties and temperature resistance.
- The textile grade (TG) PAN polymer is significantly cheaper than carbon fibre (CF) grade PAN polymer.
- The present work reports a comprehensive study on the wet-spinning of the blends of TG and CF grade PAN to develop low-cost PAN fibres.
- This work consists of the preparation of polymer dope solutions of varying compositions and understanding its rheological behaviour to predict the spinnability.
- The selected compositions of the blends of CF and TG PAN were used to spun precursor fibres through wet-spinning method
- The precursor fibres were analysed for their mechanical properties and surface analysis.

Fig.1 Carbon fibre value chain

Study of rheological parameters and wet-spinning of precursor fibres

Fig.2 Flow-sweep analysis of selected PAN polymer solutions at 30°C

Fig.3 TG, CF and TG70/CF30 precursor fibres (from left to right)

Optimisation of spinning parameters

Fig.4 Effect of change in extrusion volume on (a) tenacity (b) modulus of PAN fibres

Fig.5 Effects of jet-stretch on (a) tenacity (b) modulus of PAN fibres

Properties of precursor fibres

Fig.6 Effects of extrusion volume on surface morphology CF PAN fibres

Fig.7-8 Mechanical properties of PAN fibre samples

References:

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